

An assessment of the contribution of different factors in the development of youth-led enterprises in Nyanza district, Rwanda

Sixbert Sangwa*^{1,2}

¹Africa Leadership University, Rwanda

²Open Christian University, South Africa

*Email: sangwamukiza@gmail.com

Abstract: This descriptive study sought to establish the factors that hinder the development of youth entrepreneurship in Rwanda, particularly in Nyanza district. A target of 240 business units was used, from which a sample of 150 people was chosen as the representative. Probabilistic and non-probability sampling techniques were used to create a sampling frame. Stratified sampling was one of the probability techniques used to ensure that various types of youth-led businesses were included in the survey. Data were collected using self-administered questionnaires, a maintenance guide and an observation method. The data collected was analyzed using the Statistical package for Social Scientist software. The results were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics and were presented using tables. The findings revealed that a majority of youth had limited access to credit, market, entrepreneurship training and business development services during the start-up and growth phase, with many youth engaged in business motivated by socio-economic factors such as unemployment. The study concluded that poor access and unavailability of credit and may slow down the development of youth entrepreneurship if there are no favorable credit systems to promote youth entrepreneurship. The provision of entrepreneurship education and training should also be improved, hence its introduction into primary and secondary school levels and tailored in a manner that can equip the youth with skills to start their own enterprises and not just passing examinations. Furthermore, it was recommended to adopt youth-friendly policies and regulations, such as making the bidding system favorable, offering tax exemptions to startups, and relaxing licensing regulations.

Key words: Youth entrepreneurship and Access to credits, Entrepreneurship Education, Business Development Services, Market Accessibility, Government Policies and Regulations.

I. INTRODUCTION

Overview

This chapter presents the background, statement of the problem, Justification and significance of the study, objectives (General and specific), research questions, the study scope and the conceptual framework.

Background to the Study

Africa is fortunate to have a youthful population, where more than 60% of Africans are young people under 35 (Nathan, 2018), who are also expected to double by 2055 (Mohamed, 2017). However, while youth undeniably represents the greatest strength and resources (Richard, 2017), a powerful opportunity for accelerating economic growth (UN, 2018) that any country can have to boost its socio-economic development (Tinker, 2017); the African youth population continues to face significant challenges. Reports from around the world indicate that youth unemployment is one of the persistent problems facing all nations (Richard, 2017; UN, 2018; Hila et al.,2018). As a result of growing youth unemployment, young people are experiencing increased levels of poverty and social exclusion, and there is a widening economic gap between older and younger generations (Sixbert, 2016). In addition, although a large and growing African population of young people represents the highest hope for their countries in the coming decades (Monica et al.,2014); It has been argued that their increasing academic attainments make it more difficult, for most sub-Saharan African countries to create satisfactory youth employment opportunities (Joseph et al.,2018) as unemployment begins as soon as they are eligible to work (Hila et al.,2018).

Global public policy has been to eliminate unemployment and achieve full employment for the nations of the world, but the global unemployment rate still indicates high levels of youth unemployment rates (ILO, 2018). On this, Sixbert (2016) claims that:

So many conferences have been pointing on the dangerous argument that limiting population growth is a prerequisite for sustainable development. Though young people have been treated as new burden to the development, policy makers ignore an important thing: *“The creativity of humans is the earth’s greatest resource with which we can make the world a better place even in the face of a growing population. A youthful population is an opportunity to any society”*

Recognizing that young people have their unique creativities and the loss associated with the high social cost of unemployment and knowing that there is no other way to serve people unless economy; different governments, education institutions, companies, and other nonprofit organizations opted to design and implement interventions that facilitate resources for the youngsters to effectively cope with unemployment experiences and profit from them to grow and flourish in the broader context of their career development.

Rwanda, in particular, has put in place a number of affirmative action programs to address unequal access to economic opportunities (Joseph et al., 2018), among which the promotion of youth entrepreneurship was considered as fundamental to achieving MDG 8, where youth entrepreneurship was seen as fundamental tool for improving the low rate of enterprise and job creation for young people (Wise,2015; Turton & Herrington, 2013).

These interventions include the stimulation of Job creation through a stable macroeconomic framework, structural policies which encourage innovation, skills, and business development and forging partnerships for scaling up investments in decent jobs for youth (OECD,2014; Moore et

al., 2017). In this regards, the Rwandan government set up the National Youth Council (NYC) in 2011, which is one of the mechanisms enabling young people to contribute effectively to national development. Today, the council's achievements include promoting youth entrepreneurship through capacity building. Gradually, the council extended its activities from the center to all administrative units, up to the cell level. National Youth Council officials report that it has contributed greatly to the effective implementation of its programs (Times Reporter, 2012).

Since 2011, the government of Rwanda has seen youth entrepreneurship as a way to reduce increasing yearly youth unemployment rates. Youth and women entrepreneurship was made a potential pillar in the Rwandan Government's Economic Development and poverty reduction strategies (EDPRS), where the government is committed to creating more than 200,000 new off-farm jobs yearly (UNDP, 2018). A Business Development Fund (BDF) was established and the regulatory procedures have changed slightly in favour of new start-ups. According to Julius (2017), the private sector has also taken up the challenge of promoting youth entrepreneurship to help create jobs. This has provided an opportunity for enterprising and innovative young Rwandans to obtain funding to implement or develop their business ideas.

Rwanda, as one of the African countries, has a growing economy that relies heavily on subsistence agriculture (FAO, 2018). The recent report of the Food Agricultural Organization (FAO, 2018) indicates that nearly 70% of the country's population is farmers, but agriculture accounts for only 33% of the national Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Although few people are involved in industry and services, these last are more productive than agriculture (MINECOFIN, 2015). On the other hand, Rwanda, like many other African countries, is blessed to have a very youthful population, where young people represent nearly half of the total Rwandan population (Jean Philbert,2018). Unfortunately, the majority of the unemployed people are youth, especially

those who graduate each year from different universities and vocational schools, where almost 52% of young graduates suffer unemployment (Staff, 2017; World Bank, 2019).

Recognizing that youth unemployment generally becomes a political, economic or social challenge, also taking into account that the industry and services sectors are six times more productive than agriculture (MINECOFIN, 2015) and seeking to develop home-grown solutions; the government of Rwanda has made productivity and youth employment a mandatory topic by promoting youth entrepreneurship and business development. By adapting entrepreneurship as a new strategy to develop, facilitate and strengthen youth economic participation (Musengi-Ajulu, 2010), it is thought that this will facilitate the transition to a knowledge-based economy. However, after noting consistent failure of youth entrepreneurship, the government and its civil society partners have been carrying out an awareness campaign to promote Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) for youth entrepreneurship and life skills development across the country, but results remain unconvincing (Rwanda Focus, 2013).

Believing that youth entrepreneurship would contribute to job creation, especially self-employment, youth entrepreneurship has become a subject for government, private institutions and different nongovernmental organizations. The Rwandan government and some non-profit organizations have taken up the challenge of youth entrepreneurship by encouraging young people to acquire job-specific skills through TVET programs and by funding startups that have ultimately failed.

However, one can argue that SME sector, in Rwandan context, is a new subject as a country with almost 12 million inhabitants (NISR,2012), only 2% of the total population have businesses registered with the Rwanda Development Board (RDB), recognizing also that an indeterminate

number of entrepreneurs own more than one company (RDA, 2018). However, this number has increased compared to the 2008 data, where a 65% increase in the number of registered firms is a positive sign to achieve the objective of the Economic Development and Poverty Reduction Strategy (EDPRS) which aims to create 1.4 million non-farm jobs (Hategeka, 2016). According to Simon et al. (2017), the higher the rate of entrepreneur in a country could increase its economy growth and it may also reduce the number of unemployment and increase competition in Rwanda to trigger economic growth (Ellen, 2018).

According to different researchers, a strong small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) sector is a major contributor to the country's economy, contributing to the gross domestic product (GDP) by reducing unemployment, reducing poverty and promotion of entrepreneurship activity (Wise, 2015; Turton and Herrington, 2013; [Kilimani](#), 2017); hence the role of SMEs in the development of the country is important (Bayati & Taghavi, 2007). However, like anywhere in the world, SMEs in Rwanda still face many challenges, despite their importance and their contribution to economic growth, which hampers business growth. As the business environments, as well as certain factors, have become very complex and dynamic; it is obvious that the obstacles to the success of the company are much greater than before.

SMEs have the capacity to significantly reduce the high unemployment rate and contribute to the GDP of the local economy in Rwanda. By creating jobs and stimulating economic growth, SMEs have enormous potential for assume a greater role in the economy. As recently reported by International Labor (ILO), SMEs create 67% of global employment, regardless of country of origin income level or size of the region. Have a strong, dynamic, competitive and resilient foundation of SMEs are essential for enhancing wealth creation and social well-being, but to achieve this fully, SMEs must have sufficient and easy access to finance (World Bank 2013, Beck, 2008). With

sufficient funds, SMEs can prosper, grow and have a greater impact on the economy increased tax contributions, job creation and employment. The unanimous adoption of the Maputo Agreement by members of the Alliance for Financial Inclusion in Global Policy 2015. The Forum also highlighted the importance of access to finance for SMEs - in job creation, Economic Development and Innovation (Alliance for Financial Inclusion, 2016). In addition to helping to reduce the high unemployment rate, SMEs can be used to transform the country, by redistributing productive assets, among previously disadvantaged people. The failure rate of SMEs is high worldwide and the situation does not differ from that of Rwanda (Fang, Yuli & Hongzhi, 2009). However, Ellen (2018) considers that the rate of entrepreneurs in Rwanda is always lower than the ideal number of entrepreneurs at the international level. It is far behind Southeast Asian countries, for example Singapore, which has a 5% entrepreneurship rate in the country (Lautama, 2013).

Although entrepreneurship has been recognized as the backbone of many economies in both developed and developing countries, the contribution of youth has not yet been fully recognized (Simon et al., 2017). Young people are an important part of most economies, but at the same time they are marginalized and often victims of patriarchal prejudices. In recent decades, youth empowerment has been a common program to most government development programs. This is not surprising, since in most societies businesses set up by youth do not always do as well as the adult men in terms of growth and profitability and youth struggle more to access funding opportunities.

The failure of youth SMEs in Rwanda can be attributed to many factors and to the entrepreneurial culture. Interestingly, various researchers have confirmed that young people can run successful businesses to eventually support their families and communities, and contribute to

economic growth. This shows that not allowing young people to participate meaningfully in entrepreneurship is a loss for the nation and society.

As discussed above, Rwandan youth also faces enormous challenges compared to their former generational counterparts. Young people under the age of 35 represent nearly 70% of the Rwandan population (Aimé & Jules, 2018), but they are under-represented in the formal employment and business sectors for reasons of financial capacity, knowledge and skills, maturity, career development choices, etc. Nevertheless, only few youths in Rwanda have broken this barrier and started their own enterprises.

Although there have been significant changes in youth entrepreneurship in Rwanda, the challenges young people face in this regard are still flourishing. Therefore, the government should focus on this problem and try to improve the number of entrepreneurial aspects in Rwanda. Moreover, it is not only the government that should be interested in this problem. Citizens could also help increase the rate of entrepreneurs by becoming entrepreneurs.

Several factors can motivate citizens of a country to become entrepreneurs. From the point of view of education, it has been argued that the level of education in Rwanda does not improve the number of entrepreneurs in the country. This is because Rwanda's educational standards are still very poor in encouraging young citizens to become entrepreneurs (Times Reporter, 2011; Aimé & Jules, 2018). There are also several causes: most Rwandan citizens do not really know the policies for starting a business, the lack of good facilities that could help them start the business, and the most interesting thing that can prevent people to become entrepreneurs is corruption. Therefore, this research attempts to gather accurate data on the influence of youth entrepreneurship in Rwanda.

It's believed that the results can be a reference for the government to develop the number of new entrepreneurs in Rwanda and can also become a reference for those wishing to open a business in Rwanda. Given the current situation of Rwandan youth SMEs, it is necessary to explore the hindering factors to improve/enhance Rwanda's SME performance. Therefore, the objective of this study was to identify the factors that influence the performance of youth SMEs in Nyanza, Rwanda.

Problem statement

Current evidences from around the world indicate that young people are facing particular problems and challenges in gaining access to the labor market or available entrepreneurship opportunities in order to find secure employment (ILO,2010 - 2018; World Bank, 2010a; Ardington et al.,2013; United Nations Swaziland,2013; Levinsohn et al.,2014; Ryder, 2016; [Kilimani](#), 2017). They do face unprecedented levels of challenge around the world in accessing the careers they want to pursue. Their families are often actively involved in helping them find work but however, it keeps being a challenge. The same reports highlight that the youth unemployment crisis is having a profound effect on young people and the societies in which they live (Klasen & Woolard, 2009; OECD 2010; World Youth Report, 2003).

In response to global issue that threatens to undermine the very fabric of our society, the Rwandan government created the National Youth Council (NYC), the Business Development Fund (BDF) and implemented various policies to promote youth employability, encouraging the creation of youth enterprises as an alternative source of employment, one of Rwanda Vision 2020's flagship projects under the social pillar.

However, despite the implementation of different policies, it is clear that either policymakers or implementers cannot reach all the need for unemployment inside the country. The analysis of the Rwandan employment ecosystem shows both increasing youth unemployment rate year after year and young people's inability to start new businesses as well as consistent failure of new youth ventures (Nic & Jos, 2013), hence a need to investigate youth's competitive performance and policy gaps in the sector.

Study Objectives

General objectives

The purpose of this study was to establish the factors hindering the development of youth entrepreneurship in Nyanza district/ Rwanda

Specific objectives

In regards to the above problem discussion, the study has had the following specific objectives:

1. To determine how credit availability and accessibility influence the development of entrepreneurship among the youth in Nyanza district.
2. Examine the influence of access to entrepreneurship education and training on the development of entrepreneurship among young people in Rwanda
3. Examine the influence of access to business development services on the development of youth entrepreneurship in Rwanda
4. To establish how access to markets influence the development of entrepreneurship among the youth in Nyanza and Rwanda generally

5. Examine how social economic factors influence the development of entrepreneurship among the youth in Nyanza district in Rwanda

Research Questions

It is suggested to focus this doctoral research on the following points:

1. How does credit accessibility and availability influence the development of entrepreneurship among the youth in Nyanza District?
2. To what extent does access to entrepreneurship education and training influence the development of entrepreneurship among the youth in Nyanza District?
3. How does the accessibility to Business development services influence the development of entrepreneurship among the youth in Nyanza District?
4. To what extent does market access influence the development of entrepreneurship among the youth in Nyanza District?
5. How do the social economic factors influence the development of entrepreneurship among the youth in Nyanza District?

Significance of the Study

The Government of Rwanda, with the aim of promoting economic development through a well-established SME sector, has established the National Youth Council (NYC) and the Business Development Fund (BDF) so that youth-led SMEs have easy access to finance without any obstacles or with minimal obstacles. While the Business Development Fund has a mandate of educating SME personnel about financial management, planning and other economic matters; the

National Youth Council (NYC) is mandated to advocate for policies that are responsive to the problems facing the youth and to implement youth economic empowerment strategies as well as to educate the youth on finding solutions to their problems, mobilize them to take part in decision-making processes and in their activities and to join decision-making organ (NYC,2011). Given the whispered poor policy implementation and design as well as the fact that Given that the study was among the first few which have assessed the contributions government policies, the study will serve as a source of baseline information for other future studies that will be conducted in the same context.

Since the study consists of an exploratory approach that attempts to collect different factors that influence the failure/success of new youth startups in Rwanda, collect best practices of successful youth entrepreneurial ventures, and explore gaps in policy making, it is believed to provide the best recommendations on can be done to stimulate a way that tackles the current high unemployment rate. It tries also to establish a reliable and easily accessible platform on which academicians and prospective social entrepreneurs as well as policy makers can build on. The study is therefore important to generate insights that can be used by future entrepreneurs as well as the government and other economic actors to promote youth entrepreneurship as an alternative source of employment. It's believed also helps the government to achieve the current SDGs by identifying factors that influence the development of youth entrepreneurship and proposing recommendations that would help address relevant policy failures.

Basic assumptions of the study

Respondents were assumed to be small business owners, past and prospective entrepreneurs and would provide specific information when answering research questions. It was

also assumed that the size of the sample chosen was adequate to allow the researcher to make a valid conclusion about the population.

Determinations of the study

The study was limited to small businesses. The study focused on young entrepreneurs who perform various types of legally accepted economic activities in Nyanza District of Rwanda. The young people selected for the study were expected to be between 18 and 35 years old.

Definitions of significant terms

Micro and Small Enterprises (MSE): These are businesses operating in formal and informal sectors of the economy and employing between 5 and less than 20 employees.

Self-employment: Practice of owning and operating a small enterprise as a means of livelihood; working for one's own account, often in the informal sector.

Social economic factors: Participation of youth in business based on age, gender, marital status, economic and social status.

Under-employment: A situation in which an individual is employed, but not in the desired capacity, whether in terms of compensation, hours or level of skill and experience.

Unemployment: Situation where people who are willing and capable of working are unable to find suitable paid employment.

Youth: Young people between ages 18-35 years of age.

Youth entrepreneurs: Young people who are engaged in any type of legal business.

Youth entrepreneurship: This involves acquainting young people and students with the realities and opportunities of small-business employment and ownership.

Conceptual Framework

Below is the conceptual framework of the study that attempts to establish relationships between the particular variables in this study. The diagram below identifies the variables required in the research survey and maps for further investigation as well as a synthesis of the literature on how to explain a phenomenon.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual framework

Source: Own figure

As it can be noted, the Development of Youth Entrepreneurship (DYE) can be described as a function of five independent variables which are: Access to credit (AC), Access to

Entrepreneurship education(AEE), Access to business development services (ABDS), access to market (AM) and socioeconomic factors (SEF). And mathematically: $DYE = f(AC, AEE, ABDS, AM, SEF)$, provided that young people possess an entrepreneurial mindset and the government regulations are favorable (Detailed in 5.9).

II. METHODOLOGY

Introduction

This chapter outlines the methodology which was used in the study. The following topics were discussed; research design, target population, sampling procedure, data collection method and instruments.

For this research work, the researcher used several techniques to gather primary and secondary data required such as literature research internet, discussion with key informants, published documents, newspapers, questionnaires and interviews.

The literature research helped in acquiring secondary data which were analyzed in order to have better insights on the economic and market situation in Rwanda, and in particular, the youth business development. The data was also used in providing background information on the study area and the youth entrepreneurship, which acted as the research subjects. Different documents that informed our research include past studies and reports considered relevant to the research problem, policy papers and development plans from different institutions.

On the other hand, discussions were conducted with the key informants who were anticipated to be staff in different nonprofits; representative of youth associations/ cooperative, business

owners, government officials and education actors. Conversations were recorded to extract needed data on the subject.

Finally, young people, owners of different businesses in Nyanza district and staff from relevant employment promotion institutions were interviewed with a formal questionnaire, which had both open and closed questions.

Research design

A descriptive survey design was used in this cross-sectional study. Borg and Gall (1999) have pointed out that the survey design is well suited to studies in which individuals are used as a unit of analysis to measure generalizations. The survey design was better suited to this study because the data needed for the analysis had to be collected from a large population, in which it might be difficult to observe the characteristics of each individual. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), descriptive research determines and reports on the current state of affairs and attempts to describe the behaviors, attitudes, values and possible characteristics of these objects. Schindler and Cooper (2003) observed that descriptive studies are structured with questions to be clearly stated. The descriptive design was selected in this study as it would allow the researcher to gather numerical and descriptive data to assess the relationship between the variables. This would allow the researcher to produce statistical information on factors affecting the performance of young start-ups in Rwanda.

Target population

The population of interest in this research consisted of 240 youth entrepreneurs between (14 - 35) years from Nyanza district engaged in various business activities which are licensed and have a permanent physical location. The study focused on micro and small enterprises owned and

operated by youth entrepreneurs involved in the provision various goods and services, the main financial institutions of focus were; Micro Finance Institutions, Commercial banks with special emphasis on Youth Enterprise Development Fund. Given the diversity and nature of the data required to answer the research questions, the use of several target groups was adopted, the target population therefore consisted of out of school youth who are self-employed. In addition, one administrative official from Business Development Fund and one official from a financial institution were also interviewed.

Sampling size and procedures

The study used both probability and non- probability sampling techniques to create a sampling frame for youth run enterprises. Stratified sampling was one of the probability techniques used in order to ensure that various types of youth run enterprises were included in the survey. The study population was stratified into: Service Businesses (e.g. Cyber cafes, Mobile Money, Haircutting Saloons, moto transport, Repairs and Maintenance); Retail businesses (e.g. Bars and Butcheries, Cosmetics, Retail shops, Electronics/Accessories) and Wholesale distribution (e-g- Hardware and wholesale premises).

Non probability sampling was employed once the strata were identified. This included the use of purposive sampling to select one District administrative officer in charge of Youth, administrative member of Business Development Fund at the district level and another officer from a micro finance institution involved in loan extension to the youth in the area. A sample size of 150 youth entrepreneurs was selected from the target population using systematic random sampling technique where every business in each of the strata had a chance of being selected, the

below table describes the number of respondents who were selected from each of the strata in order to form the study population.

Type of business	Number	Sample Size
Services Businesses	122	79
Cybercafe	15	9
Mobile money shops	20	12
Hotel and restaurant	25	15
Saloons/haircutting	27	16
Repairs/Maintenance	25	15
Motorbike /Taxes	20	12
Retail businesses	100	60
Electronics/Accessories	10	6
Retail shops	10	6
Bar and Butchery	20	12
Cosmetics	10	6
Bookshops	10	6
Property dealers	15	9
Fruit /Vegetable vendors	25	15
Wholesale distribution	18	11
Wholesalers	8	5
Hardware	10	6
TOTAL	240	150

Table 4.1: Sampling frame

The researcher used a sample size of 60% of the accessible target population. In addition, a district Administrative officer, the director of BDF at the district level and another officer from a financial institution were also interviewed. According Krijieie and Morgan's (1970) Table of determining sample sizes, for a target population of 240, a sample of 150 was found desirable for this study as computed in Table 4.1.

Data collection methods

This study collected quantitative and qualitative data using a range of quantitative and qualitative approaches and techniques. The two primary quantitative data were collected using an online survey (google form semi-structured questionnaire) on key variables such as socio-economic and demographic characteristics, skills development, access market and the commercial opportunities available.

Pilot Study

A pilot study was conducted to test the reliability and validity of the questionnaires. The purpose of the pilot survey was to ascertain whether the design of the questions made sense, whether the questions were clear and easy to understand and whether the recorded answers were complete and how long it would take to complete the questionnaire, the preliminary test would also allow the researcher to verify if the variables collected could easily be processed and analyzed. The pre-test was conducted on a sample of 10% of respondents. All the questions that were interpreted differently during the preliminary test were reworded so that they could have the same meaning for all respondents. The views expressed by the respondents during the pre-tests were analyzed and used to improve the questionnaires before actual data collection.

Validity of instruments

The validity of an instrument refers to the extent to which an instrument measures what it is intended to measure (Kothari, 2004). A content validity test was used to measure the validity of the instrument. This type of validity measured the extent to which data collected using a particular instrument represented a specific area of indicators or the content of a particular concept (Mugenda and Mugenda, 1999). An expert in project monitoring, entrepreneurship and data analysis received the tools needed to assess the extent to which it was possible to measure and determine the content of a particular concept.

In the above regards, the researcher borrowed validation strategies from business analysts who for many years have struggled with determining whether questionnaires assessing intelligence and attitudes really measure what is intended. Validation strategies include:

- **content-related:** evidence that the items and domains of an instrument are appropriate and comprehensive relative to its intended measurement concept(s), population and use;
- **construct-related:** evidence that relationships among items, domains, and concepts conform to *a priori* hypotheses concerning logical relationships that should exist with other measures or characteristics of participants.

To establish validity, it is necessary to examine the logical relationships that should exist between evaluation measures. In the context of the researcher, it was expected that successful young entrepreneurs would have access to the market, funds, business development services and a favorable socio-economic environment; and one would expect the majority of exceptional start-ups to receive some form of government support; hence this correlation expressed in the questionnaires.

Reliability of instruments

The instrument reliability was measured by the test-retest technique by administering the questionnaires to a group of people with characteristics similar to the actual size of the sample. The test was repeated after two weeks. The scores obtained from the two tests were correlated to obtain the coefficient of reliability. Spearman's correlation coefficient of 0.7 was considered acceptable.

Data collection procedures

The researcher collected primary and secondary data to formulate conclusions and recommendations. Primary data were collected using a structured online questionnaire for remote districts and paper questionnaires for nearby districts, a structured interview guide, and an observation method. Where appropriate, the questionnaires were sent directly to the respondents by the researcher because most of the companies in the study area were very close to each other. The interviews were also conducted by the researcher personally at a time and place that is convenient for the respondents. The observation was done the same day the respondents were administered the questionnaires at their place of work or business premises. Secondary data were collected in trade manuals, economic surveys, government reports, newspapers and periodicals.

Data analysis

The Analysis of Data began with pre-processing of the data collected through modifications to detect errors and omissions and to make corrections as far as possible. This involved careful analysis of completed questionnaires to ensure that the data collected was accurate and consistent with other information collected. The data collected was coded by the researcher for efficiency in order to reduce the responses given by respondents to a small number of classes. Once the coding

is complete, the data has been classified based on common characteristics and attributes. The raw data was then assembled and compiled into statistical tables for further analysis. This facilitated the summation of elements and the detection of errors and omissions. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. This involved the use of measures of central tendency such as mean, mode, median, and normal distribution measures. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to facilitate the statistical analysis of the data. Content analysis was applied to qualitative data to identify patterns, themes and biases. Finally, all the data was stored on electronic copies and printed in tabular form.

Limitations of the study

The time constraint was a limiting factor because the study had to be concluded in a very short time. The availability of funds was also a limiting factor for the study since the researcher was self-sponsored. There was no guarantee that respondents would return all the completed questionnaires, or that the interviewees would answer all of the questions posed to them in a comprehensive manner.

Ethical issues

The researcher tried to obtain the informed consent of the respondents before committing to collecting data in the field. The researcher informed and explained the objectives of the research in order to solicit the informed consent of the respondents. The high level of confidentiality of information provided by respondents during interviews or questionnaires was maintained.

Operationalization variables

The measurement of the various variables in this study will be undertaken as shown in the below table:

Table 4.2: Operationalization of Variables

Objective	Variable/Indicator <u>Independent</u>	Measure	Measurement Scale	Tools of Analysis	Type of Analysis
To find out the extent to which credit availability and access influence the development of youth entrepreneurship in Nyanza, Rwanda.	Loans borrowed	Number of youth who accessed credit	Ratio	Mean Percentages	Descriptive statistics
To examine how access to entrepreneurial education and training influence the development of youth entrepreneurship in Nyanza, Rwanda	Qualification of entrepreneur education and training	Number youth who accessed entrepreneurship education	Ordinal	Mean Percentages Frequencies	Descriptive statistics, Inferential statistics
To determine how access to Business development services influence the development of youth entrepreneurship.	Business development services	Number of support services	Ordinal	Mean Percentages	Descriptive statistics
To establish how access to markets influence the development of youth entrepreneurship in Nyanza, Rwanda	Market access	Number of youth with market access	Ordinal	Mean Percentages	Descriptive statistics
To examine the social economic factors affecting the development of youth entrepreneurship in Nyanza, Rwanda	Social economic factors	Number of youth in business in gender terms	Nominal	-	Descriptive Statistics

III. DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Introduction

This chapter presents the analysis, presentation and interpretation of data from data collected from youth-led enterprises in different districts of Rwanda, about the factors that influence the development of youth entrepreneurship. The study sampled 150 youth (5 respondents from Nyanza district) operating a business, including those funded by the Business Development Fund (BDF) and other financial institutions. The data were interpreted according to the research questions. The analysis was performed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The results were presented in the form of frequency tables and percentages. The researcher also interviewed the district's director of business development and another Youth Empowerment for Global Opportunities (YEGO) center officer.

Questionnaire return rate

Of the 150 questionnaires sent to the young entrepreneurs in the study, 145 were returned, giving a response rate of 97%.

Characteristics of respondents

Table 5. 1: Composition of respondents by gender

Age	Gender		Female	Percent	Total	Percent
	Male	Percent				
18-21	6	4.1	4	2.7	10	6.8
22- 26	20	13.8	10	6.9	30	20.7
27 - 30	24	16.6	12	8.3	36	24.9
31 - 35	40	27.6	29	20	69	47.6

The data in Table above show that young men are likely to start their own business at an early age compared to their female counterparts. At a later age, there are also more men (27.6%) business

owners than women (20%). This aligns with Dr. Charles and Charles’s (2018) research which explained it in terms of mindset and culture.

The highest percentage of respondents (47.6%) was between 31 and 35 years old, the lowest between 18 and 21 years of age and was (6.8%). This indicates that older young people are more involved in entrepreneurship than younger people. This can be explained by what Martin (2011) called “Resilience”. According to him, Older youth already know about the negatives and these have built their resilience such that this resilience allows them to bounce back after defeat and try again, unscathed. The entrepreneurial path is littered with pitfalls and roadblocks; young entrepreneurs need the capacity to come back again and again relentlessly.

Composition of respondents by education level

The graph below shows the levels of education that youth entrepreneurs had attained before starting business.

Figure 5.1: Youth Entrepreneurs Education Attainment

The level of education of entrepreneurs was measured to determine if education can influence the development of youth entrepreneurship. The data in the above table shows that a majority

(51.7%) of young entrepreneurs start businesses after completing high school and technical / vocational training (20.7%). The percentage of those who engage in business after completing university (3.4%) is relatively low.

It can be argued from the findings that education and culture affect entrepreneurship on many levels. Primary and secondary education provides the basic reading, writing and numeracy skills necessary for entrepreneurship. Similarly, Wise (2016) observed that business owners with education and management experience are more able to find ways to activate a business than others who have no experience or education; hence lack management skills. In addition, his studies found a positive correlation between entrepreneurship opportunities and levels of education.

Education is therefore a means of increasing entrepreneurship in factor-based economies and the absolute necessity of undertaking it in the developing countries at a later stage. Like Jacek and Anna (2013), the supply of higher education and training is classified in the category of efficiency enhancers. Efficiency enhancers, including higher education and training, play a crucial role in strengthening entrepreneurship in efficiency-oriented economies.

Type of business activities

The percentage of youth businesses engaged in the provision of services was 52.9% and 39.8% for those providing goods in the retail trade and 6.8% for the wholesale distribution. The percentage of young people engaged in the retail trade is higher than that of wholesalers. The majority of young people seem to be concentrated in service firms in relation to retail trade, as shown in the below Table.

Table below shows the various types of enterprises that the youth were engaged in.

Type of business	Frequency	Percentage
Services Businesses		
Cybercafe	9	6.2
Mobile money shops	12	8.3
Hotel and restaurant	15	10.3
Saloons/haircutting	16	11
Repairs/Maintenance	14	9.6
Motorbike /Taxes	11	7.5
Retail businesses	52.9	
Electronics/Accessories	6	4.1
Retail shops	5	3.4
Bar and Butchery	12	8.3
Cosmetics	6	4.1
Bookshops	6	4.1
Property dealers	9	6.2
Fruit /Vegetable vendors	14	9.6
Wholesale distribution	39.8	
Wholesalers	4	2.7
Hardware	6	4.1

Table 5.2: Types of enterprises that youth were engaged in

The fact that more young people are engaged in the service sector than in the sale of goods can be explained by a variety of reasons. First, the sale of goods is a riskier activity, and as Martin (2011) explained, young people did go through all the negatives and have not yet built their resilience, hence they worry taking risk. Secondly, as we have seen above, young people are likely to start a business after high school and they do not have enough money to start big businesses.

They opt for the creation of small service activities such as Mobile Money, IREMBO and other service outlets offering a range of services without capital investment. Third, sales of goods require cooperation and networking skills that young people have not accumulated. However, there is also considerable competition in this sector as many of their non-school counterparts still choose to start this type of business.

Objective 1: To find out the extent to which credit availability and access influence the development of youth entrepreneurship in Nyanza, Rwanda.

Availability and access to credit are critical to the development of youth entrepreneurship, as they provide youth with start-up capital and expansion capital. The ease with which start-up capital can be raised is critical in determining the rate at which new businesses can be created and existing businesses expanded. The researcher wanted to know to what extent access to credit and its availability could influence the development of entrepreneurship among young people.

Source of startup capital

Data presented below shows the different sources from which the respondents acquired their startup capital.

Figure 5.2: Youth Entrepreneurs' Source of Startup Capital

The graph shows that 41.4% of young people mobilized their starting capital through their personal savings, against 63.4% thanks to the help of the family. From the results in above table, it is evident that a majority of young people increased their starting capital either through their personal savings or through the support of their families. Only 5.5% of them raised their starting capital in the form of a bank loan. The percentage of young people who acquired start-up capital in the youth enterprise fund was 10.3%. The above findings can have double-sided explanations.

First, youth do not have access to credits for several reasons. A variety of studies found that lending application procedures and repayment rules hinders access to credit finance by youth in many countries. Banking institutions require collateral to be one of the prerequisites for access to credit facilities. As David Muhinda (2019), Rwandan businessman states: *“business people in Rwanda also face a challenge of competition which is very high, yet the purchasing power is low, accessibility of capital is still a challenge and bank interests are very high.”* This becomes a constraint for small-scale youth participation in SMEs. Most of them do not have any title deeds or tangible assets to present as collateral against loans. Generally accepted physical guarantees are land that is not owned by young entrepreneurs. This is similar to the recent study conducted by Ann Chebet (2016) in Kenya, which also found that higher interest rates on credit discourage young entrepreneurs from borrowing, reducing access to credit financing between them. Every business needs financing; the amount of the interest rate charged is sometimes related to the security of the loan and the use for which it is to be used, or the nature of the business.

Secondly, young entrepreneurs may also fear taking bank loans due to dealing with the negativity of well-meaning friends and family members who think they will be bankrupt if they realize their dream of business. There is also the added burden of self-doubt and fear that opponents are right. Fear of failure is a personality trait that results in the avoidance of the possibility of

failure irrespective of the prevailing circumstances. Realizing your dream of raising money from a bank to start your own business requires a lot of strength and determination. This fear may be associated with a lack of experience in investing and repaying loans, which affects their ability to obtain loans for investments with credit institutions. Some youths may generally have qualified for a loan, but have in mind that they have to strain to repay the loans. Young entrepreneurs often still feel nervous or even scared about getting into debt. Since youth are more responsible for their financial operations and budgeting in their businesses, lack of business experience and financial management skills can undermine their confidence in requesting bank loans. Given that the data indicate that young people are likely to start a business after completing secondary school, it can be argued that they may not have some pertinent knowledge and skills to engage profitably in entrepreneurship. This is similar to what was confirmed by another study in Kenya which found that graduates had no trouble raising funds from banks compared to their non-graduates counterparts.

Hindrances of obtaining credit

The below table shows how some of the barriers faced by young people in their efforts to access credit to start a business have been classified. 70.3% of young people showed that the heaviness of credit acquisition procedures was the main obstacle, while 67.5% of respondents cited the second most serious problem, namely the lack of collaterals. The lack of a business plan was the least serious obstacle with a percentage of 48.3%.

Rating of hindrances of obtaining credit

Challenges	Ranking			
	1	2	3	4
Interest rate	90	45	10	0
Percentage	62	31	7	0
Lack of security	98	25	15	7
Percentage	67.5	17.2	10.3	5
Lack of Business plan	70	64	11	0
Percentage	48.3	44.1	7.6	0
Low amount loan	79	56	9	1
Percentage	54.5	38.6	6.7	0.7
Cumbersome procedures	102	35	7	1
Percentage	70.3	24.1	4.8	0.7

Table 5.3: Rating of hindrances of obtain credits

Data from this table confirms the previous assumptions that lending application procedures and repayment rules hinders access to credit finance by youth. The table itself confirms that higher interest rates on bank loans is also a hindrance to youth access on credits. Qualitative data collected from a focus group discussion with district officials and representatives of micro-finance, also confirmed that obtaining a bank loan would involve tedious procedures, especially for jobless clients who want to start a business. They need to present a collateral which the bank will visit and determine its monetary value, the client is then asked to satisfy all the other requirements; a process that may take months.

Measures to improve credit availability and access

A majority of respondents felt that procedures and requirements for individual access to credit from the Business Development Fund should be relaxed. Others have suggested increasing the loan amount to individual borrowers. Some have suggested that viable business plans should be accepted as a guarantee to secure funds from financial institutions rather than real collaterals.

This aligned with an interview with Adrian Busingye (2019), the CEO East African Grocers Ltd who understands that:

Limited access to finance, especially for SME's. It's difficult for SMEs to acquire loans from financial institutions due to different factors such as lack of or limited securities. Thus limited entry and maintenance of business. Competition and limited market availability due to customer tastes and preferences and international products, are also a hindrance. Limited raw materials and resources to boost business, particularly production firms, and high import dependence, are also a challenge. Inconsistent application of tax incentives and tax import duties are usually high, and then there is high advertising costs.

Objective 2: To examine how access to entrepreneurial education and training influence the development of youth entrepreneurship in Nyanza, Rwanda

The data collected and presented below are intended to examine how access to entrepreneurial education and training influence the development of youth entrepreneurship in Nyanza, Rwanda. The acquisition of entrepreneurship training prior to the creation of a business is essential to help identify the business opportunity as well as its implementation. Promoting youth entrepreneurship education during their schooling was seen as essential to developing youth entrepreneurship.

The following table shows whether the respondents had received any form of entrepreneurship education prior to starting the business.

Figure 5.3: Youth's access to Entrepreneurship Train before starting a business

The majority of respondents (72.4%) confirmed that they did not receive any entrepreneurship training before starting their own business, while only 27.6% confirmed having received it.

Observation shows that economic uncertainties, and the limited supply in formal paid jobs and other career opportunities, pushed 72,4% of respondent young people into self-employment, what was called 'entrepreneurship by necessity'. However, they are neither prepared nor equipped with the requisite skills and knowledge needed to establish and manage a business successfully.

This can be explained by the existence of very few training providers in relation to the needs of young people in the country. In group discussions, entrepreneurs pointed out that, in many cases, entrepreneurship training firms charge relatively high costs that no youth can afford to attend the training. However, the role of education in cultivating entrepreneurial mindset remains intact. An entrepreneurial mindset helps young people navigate ambiguity, apply creativity to problem solving, communicate their ideas, and see obstacles and opportunities.

To this end, it is absolutely necessary. for the government, to equip teachers, recruit trusted community organizations and create alliances with the right partners to give young people access to the resources they need to become independent and transform the world.

Access to entrepreneurship training programmes

The below figure shows the percentage of the respondents who had been through entrepreneurship training programmes after starting their businesses.

Figure 5.4: Youth’s Access to Entrepreneurship training after starting business

The percentage of respondents reporting to have been through entrepreneurship training was 37.9% compared to 62.1% who had not. This confirms the existence of fewer training programs in the study area, hence big number of youth entrepreneurs have never been in training. Those who received a training before starting a business were never mentored and assisted throughout their business growth. One can also wonder how existing youth entrepreneurship programs are designed.

It can be inferred that, despite government interest in the education and training of young entrepreneurs, many (if not most) of the notable efforts have not been subject to rigorous evaluation and the knowledge about these programs’ impact remains thin. This calls for youth programs that customizes the activate curriculum to foster collaborations between corporations, foundations, government, and community partners to empower youth to create the needed change.

Commencement Level of entrepreneurship education

The below figure shows the opinions of the respondents regarding the level at which entrepreneurship education should start in institutions of learning.

Figure 5.5: Level at which Entrepreneurship education should start

Most respondents suggested that entrepreneurship education in Rwanda starts mainly at the primary level (35.9%) and 30.3% at the secondary level. Only 20% of respondents felt that this should start at the university level.

Recalling that 17.2% of youth engage in business after completing primary school, it can be suggested that entrepreneurship education should start at an early stage. Entrepreneurship education should combine experiential learning, prototyping, analysis, and communication skills to help students engage in entrepreneurial learning designed to connect their classrooms, communities, and future careers. To create maximum impact, educators are equipped with the methodology, technology, tools, and skills to help themselves and their students develop an entrepreneurial mindset.

Those who engage in the provision of entrepreneurship training must adopt a real entrepreneurial approach with multiple iterations of programs, pivots and field experiences leading to a redefinition of programming and the curriculum. To create maximum impact, providers need to involve community stakeholders in this process, by working with high school educators, community organizations, local schools and public and private partners.

Objective 3: To determine how access to Business development services influence the development of youth entrepreneurship.

Youth access to business development services, such as mentoring, support networks, business clubs and incubators, increases the chances of sustaining their businesses beyond the start-up phase. The data presented below shows the percentage of respondents who received business development services before and after the start of their activities.

Figure 5.6: Youth Access to Business Development Services

A majority of respondents (73.8%) did not receive any type of business development services before and after the start of their operations. Only 26.2% confirmed receiving business support services before starting their business. This could have been due to the limited availability or access to these services in the region.

It is essential to direct business development services to provide services to young entrepreneurs in order to obtain adequate support. Otherwise, young people can disengage from entrepreneurship based on their perception of the barriers they face. Specifically, limited access to capital, loss of cultural identity and weak institutional support capacity can influence the decision of young entrepreneurs to abandon their start-up efforts. This is also known as an uninformed entrepreneurial exit. Conversely, young entrepreneurs can leave the start-up process based on informed decision-making - for example, the existing business is unlikely to succeed. This is also known as intelligent output. Whether disengagement is voluntary or not, the importance of feasibility analysis as a learning tool can't be overemphasized.

Type of institutions providing Business development services

The graph below shows the organizations/institutions from which respondents received Business development services prior and after starting business.

Figure 5.7: Institutions providing Business Development Services

The data collected shows that 73.1% of respondents received their business development services from the government, 10.3% from NGOs and 12.4% from business companies. Respondents who received support services from the bank were the least numerous and represented approximately 9.7%. This translates a gap in public and private partnership (PPP).

What can be inferred from this is that a skills development PPP is likely to engage unskilled youth to acquire technical expertise and help young people start their own small businesses. This PPP dimension should consist of providing the youth entrepreneurs projects with key elements to meet the needs of their business. This area concerns the ability of entrepreneurs to establish relationships with the private sector (financial institutions), nonprofits, public and political organizations and different levels of government.

Fields of business development services

The following collected data shows the different fields of Business development services that the respondents had gone through.

Figure 5.8: Field of Business Development Services

The area in which most respondents received their business development service was management (44.1%), while marketers accounted for 35.8%. ICT was the area of training where respondents had the least business development at 8.3%.

This may be because the role of ICTs in business development is not yet recognized as a success factor for business in today's world. In terms of operational management, administration and marketing, technology is currently a booming business but, as is the case for most developing countries, very few experts and institutions offer this support. In addition, as a group discussion with district officials and youth leaders concluded, most ICT trainers do this for profit. As a result, very few young people can afford training. However, it was also noted that ICT trainers do not tie

it primarily to businesses, which encourages participants to consider it as an autonomous knowledge rather than incorporating it into daily activities.

Value of Business development services

A majority of respondents felt that business development and support services were important during the start-up and growth phase of the business. However, many respondents felt that they would have preferred to acquire business support services before the start-up phase.

Objective 4: To establish how access to markets influence the development of youth entrepreneurship in Nyanza, Rwanda

Market accessibility through the products of youth-led businesses is essential to ensure the sustainability of these businesses. Young people often lack the information and knowledge required to strategically market the goods and services provided by their businesses.

Marketing challenges

Type of Market challenges

Figure 5.9: Type of Market Challenges

The above chart presents the different types of market problems encountered by respondents when selling products from their businesses. Collected data shows that 42.8% of respondents felt that unfair awarding of contracts/tenders was the most important marketing challenge, while 31% reported severe competition and 23% showed poor competition. The weak demand for products from youth businesses was the least marketing challenge.

From a broad look, Rwanda has put in place strong anti-corruption policy and systems (Eiji,2017). Young people’s perception about unfair tender allocation can be linked with their lack of experience, knowledge and weak competitive strength. For any firm to bid for the tender, they must fulfill given requirements, including capacity to provide the service or commodity, since youth own relatively small enterprises, they may not compete with reputable brands. In addition, youth’s average knowledge and expertise in writing and submitting tenders properly developed in accordance with the stipulated evaluation criteria may constitute an obstacle to winning an offer.

Business connections

The data collected and presented below shows the percentage of respondents who had some business connections to assist in marketing products and services from their enterprises.

Business connections

Figure 5.10: Youth Business Connections

A majority of respondents (82.8%) said they did not have business connections to market their products and services. Only 17.2% of respondents admitted to having commercial relations to market the products of their companies.

This may be because young entrepreneurs do not find the time to attend cultural events or trade shows involving people from different locations. Alternatively, establishing online business relationships is no longer really unusual, but some people still do not understand how this is possible. This can be linked to lack of self-confidence and lack of awareness of the role of connection building, as attending events around the city is not just about making money, but friends who eventually lead to business connections of some sort.

A focus group discussion with district officials and MFI leaders argued that youth SMEs have inadequate access to market information that could benefit their businesses as well as inadequate knowledge about marketing their products both nationally and internationally.

Marketing company / institutions

Marketing is a business function that deals with the identification of customer needs and the generation of sales. This process that deals with the management of profitable customer relations should result in designing a valuable product / service which satisfies customers' needs and wants. In addition to increasing sales and customers' satisfaction by designing unique products that are valued by customers, marketing has been a tool used by many companies in building customer loyalty and increasing competitive advantage (University of South Wales, 2018).

The following data shows the type of organizations which assisted the respondents to market their goods and services.

Type of marketing institution/organization

Figure 5.11: Type of Marketing Institutions

The above chart shows that a majority of respondents (85.5%) had no organization or institution helping them to market their products, while only 2.1% received help from marketing companies. An additional 12.4% received marketing assistance from the government, but none received this assistance from NGOs.

As in the case of ICT in business, the contribution of marketing to business development may not have been taken into account. Neither young people themselves invest in marketing, nor do those who offer business development services consider this enhancer. Although the government apparently understands that marketing can contribute to the success of youth activities, it cannot meet the needs of all young entrepreneurs in this country. This absolutely depicts a knowledge gap in Rwandan youth entrepreneurship.

On the other hand, data collect from focus group discussion indicates that the biggest challenge faced by youth entrepreneurs is in packaging and labelling of Rwandan products; where they are

sometimes forced to find other companies outside of Rwanda to help them package and label their products which affects their growth because they need to deliver on time.

Marketing support required

A majority of respondents suggested that they would like the government to do more to link them to local and foreign markets. They also wanted the government to increase the consumption of their products in all departments.

Objective 5: Examine the social economic factors that influence the development of entrepreneurship among the youth in Nyanza, Rwanda

Influence of social economic factors

According to Acs Zoltan et al. (2007, 2008), a socio-economic environment in which entrepreneurship is respected and valued will serve as a catalyst for the development of youth entrepreneurship. Such an environment is conducive to start-ups, especially when the purchasing power of individuals in a population is high. A favorable economic environment ensures the durability of young enterprises.

Perception on social economic environment

The below table discloses the opinions of the respondents in relation to their social economic environment and youth entrepreneurship.

Figure 5.12: Perception on social economic environment

According to the data presented above, a sizeable proportion of the respondents (58.6%) revealed that their social economic environment was not encouraging with 41.4% disclosing it was encouraging.

Influence to start business

The table below shows the factors that influence young people to start business.

Figure 5.13: Factors influencing youth to start business

According to data presented in the above table, a majority of the respondents (57.9%) were in business due to unemployment while 17.9% it was out personal choice 13.8% was due to parent motivation with 10.4 % being motivation to supplement their incomes.

Social perception of young entrepreneurs

A majority of the entrepreneurs revealed that they were not highly valued in comparison to their counterpart in formal employment. They revealed that their parents would have preferred them to be in formal employment instead of doing business.

Government policies and regulations

Favorable government policies and regulations such as lowering the tax rate, providing subsidies, and easing licensing regulations for start-ups can significantly strengthen youth entrepreneurship development.

The following data presents respondents’ opinions on Government policies and regulations

Figure 5.14: Compliance with Government policies and regulations

The data show respondents' opinions as to whether they found it difficult to comply with government policies and regulations. The data analyzed in this table show that 71.7% of

respondents had difficulty complying with government regulations and policies, while 28.3% said no. This clearly indicates that government policies and regulations are a major challenge for the development of youth entrepreneurship.

Impact of government policies and regulations

Table below shows how the respondents ranked different government policies and regulations impacting on their enterprises.

Table 5.4: Ranking of government policies and regulations

Government policies and regulations	Ranking							
	Very serious	%	Serious	%	Less Serious	%	Not serious	%
Licensing Laws	70	48.3	39	26.9	30	20.7	6	4.2
Taxation laws	83	57.2	50	34.5	8	5.5	2	1.4
Subsidy policies	38	26.2	69	47.6	24	16.5	14	9.7
Patent/copyright laws	53	35.6	80	55.2	10	6.9	2	1.4
Competition regulations	47	34.4	56	38.6	35	24.1	7	4.8

According to the data analyzed in the above table, tax laws were the main challenge for youth-run enterprises at 57.2%, while licensing regulations ranked second. Subsidy policies were ranked as the least serious challenge with 26.2% and competition laws with 34.4%. In comments, youth business leaders argued that SMEs in Rwanda face significant compliance burdens dealing with existing regulation, where the current tax regime is both costly and difficult to comprehend.

Youth Opinions on government policies

Most respondents suggested adjusting the tax laws for youth-run businesses to make them more supportive. Respondents also indicated that they would like the government to ease the regulation of young business licensing to reduce the standards required to obtain approval from the Rwanda Standard Board (RSB), and other specialized bodies, like getting a school accredited by Higher Education Council.

Development of Youth Entrepreneurship (DYE)

Ranking of the factors contributing to youth business performance and development:

Statements	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Access to Credits	2	1.38	9	6.21	13	8.7	44	30.34	77	53.10
Access to Entrepreneurship education and Training	11	7.59	8	5.52	26	17.93	51	35.17	49	33.79
Access to Business Development Services	7	4.83	14	9.66	22	15.17	40	27.59	62	42.76
Access to Market	0	0.00	1	0.69	19	13.19	57	39.58	67	46.53
Socio-economic Factors	4	2.76	11	7.59	21	14.48	39	26.90	70	48.28

Table 5.5: Ranking of Youth Business Success factors

Respondents of this study were asked to rank the factors that contribute to the development of youth business startups in accordance with their personal understanding. When respondents were asked whether access to credits and long-term loans is a major business success factor, 30.34% agreed, 53.10% strongly agreed, 6.21% disagreed, 1.38% strongly disagreed and 8.97% remained neutral respectively. When respondents were asked if access to entrepreneurship education is a

major business factor, 35.17% agreed, 33.79% strongly agreed, 5.52% disagreed and 7.59% strongly disagreed while 17.93% remained neutral. On the question on whether respondents see access to business development services as a major business success factor, 27.76% agreed and 42.76% strongly agreed while 9.66% disagreed and 4.83% strongly disagreed against 15.15% who remained neutral. The same question was asked to understand respondents' views about whether access to market is a major business success factor and, 39.58% and 46.53% agreed and strongly agreed respectively while 0.69% disagree and 13.19% remained neutral but none strongly disagreed to this statement. Finally, respondents were asked if they consider socio-economic factors as the major contributors to business success: 48.28% strongly agreed and 26.90% agreed, 7.59% disagreed and 2.76% strongly disagreed while 14.48% remained neutral.

Correlation analysis

From the theoretical and empirical review of literature, the conceptual model to be investigated takes the form:

$$DYE = f(AC, AEE, ABDS, AM, SEF) \quad (1)$$

As advised by Insah et al. (2013), the econometric specification would involve concentrating on the cross section aspect of the Time Series Cross Section (TSCS) Model. The Generic TSCS model is of the form

$$Y_{i,t} = X_{i,t} \beta + \sum_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

where $i = 1, \dots, N$; $t = 1, \dots, T$, and $X_{i,t}$ is a K vector of exogenous variables and observations are indexed by unit i and time t . In this specification, time would be fixed since it does not vary.

The equation may thus be modified as:

$$Y_i = X_i \beta + \sum_i \epsilon_i \quad (3)$$

The estimable model for the study would thus become:

$$DYE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AC + \beta_2 AEE + \beta_3 ABDS + \beta_4 AM + \beta_5 SEF + \mu \quad (4)$$

Results and Discussion

The relationship or association that exists between the Development of Youth Enterprises (DYE) and the determinants is established. This is established using correlation analysis as shown in the below table:

Variables	Correlation coefficient
Access to Credits	0.986**
Access to Entrepreneurship education and Training	0.945**
Access to Business Development Services	0.993**
Access to Market	0.988**
Socio-economic Factors	0.985**

Table 5.6: Correlations between Development of Youth Entrepreneurship and its factors

** denotes Strong significance at the 1% and 5% levels.

It is observed that all variables have high positive correlation coefficients. Among the variables, Access to Business Development Services has the highest correlation coefficient of

0.993, followed by Access to Market (0.988), Access to credits (0.986), Socio-economic factors (0.985) and Access to Entrepreneurship Education and training (0.945). These coefficients are very high and positive, and statistically significant.

Chi Square Test

The chi-squared test results indicate that the null hypotheses, that the five factors contribute to the development of youth entrepreneurship, cannot be rejected in all cases.

Variables	Chi Square value
Access to Credits	0.000**
Access to Entrepreneurship education and Training	0.000**
Access to Business Development Services	0.000**
Access to Market	0.000**
Socio-economic Factors	0.000**

Table 5.6: Chi Square Values

** denotes Strong significance at the 1% and 5% levels.

As it can be observed, all Chi Square values tend toward zero, which theoretically means that there is no noteworthy difference between observed values and expected values (Svetlana,2019) and therefore, a high correlation between each factor and the development of youth entrepreneurship. However, due to reaching at the same results, the Chi square test only confirms

a strong correlation between each independent variable and the dependent variable but doesn't provide idea on their ascending level of correlation.

Regression analysis

Model	Multiple R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	R	Standard Error
1	1	1	65535	1	0

Table 5.7: Multiple regression factors

Predictors: (Constant), Access to Credits, Entrepreneurship Education, Business Development Services, Access to market and Socio-economic factors.

R Square is the Coefficient of Determination, which is used as an indicator of the goodness of fit. It shows how many points fall on the regression line. The R^2 value is calculated from the total sum of squares, more precisely, it is the sum of the squared deviations of the original data from the mean.

Generally, R Squared of 95% or more is considered a good fit. As it can be observed, an R^2 is 1 is extremely very good. It means that 100% of our values fit the regression analysis model. In other words, 100% of the dependent variables (y-values) are explained by the independent variables (x-values). Practically, this means that the development of youth entrepreneurship is fully explained by the five factors which are Access to Credits, Entrepreneurship Education, Business Development Services, Access to market and Socio-economic factors. This is also confirmed by the standard error of zero which means 100% precision level of the regression analysis. Similarly, the same results were obtained using ANOVA results.

ANOVA

This test splits the sum of squares into individual components that give information about the levels of variability within the regression model.

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	5	48536	9707.2	4.202	000
Residual	0	0	65535		
Total	5	48536			

Table 5.8: Anova table

- a) Dependent Variable: Development of Youth Entrepreneurship
- b) Predictors: (Constant), Access to Credits, Entrepreneurship Education, Business Development Services, Access to market and Socio-economic factors

From the above results, it's clear that our model fits the data 100% with Residual of Zero compared to the total Sum square of 48536. The **Significance F** value gives an idea of how reliable (statistically significant) the results of this study are. Lastly, the Multiple regression coefficients confirmed reliability of the used model as indicated in the below table.

Regression Analysis Output Coefficients

	<i>Standard</i>				
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	-3.965663833	0	65535	-3.96566	3.965663833
2	1.728744277	0	65535	1.728744	1.728744277
11	2.100555919	0	65535	2.100556	2.100555919
7	0	0	65535	0	0
0	0	0	65535	0	0
4	1.327501635	0	65535	1.327502	1.327501635

Table 5.9: Multiple regression coefficients

All coefficients are positive, which means that if an independent variable changes by a certain percentage, the dependent variable changes to the same percentage and in the same direction.

Summary

The main findings of this study revealed that, to a large extent, the five factors contribute to the successful development of youth entrepreneurship with an almost identical percentage. However, although all factors are closely related to the development of youth enterprises, a correlation analysis could help us rank them from the one with the strongest relationship with youth entrepreneurship development, as following: Access to Business Development Services; Access to Market; Access to credits; Socio-economic factors and Access to Entrepreneurship Education and training. It is very important to mention that there is really noticeable difference

between the contributions of each factor, as confirmed by the Chi-square test where all values are zero, which means that there is no concrete difference between observed and expected values. All coefficients denoted relationships almost equally statistically significant.

Best practices recommendations

An optional question was asked of successful young entrepreneurs to advise their colleagues on what worked best or least on the path of entrepreneurship. Most respondents mentioned that they have had a lot of downs and ups until their stood firm in their career. Some also mentioned that they were even jailed or asked to close their businesses.

The majority of respondents sought advice from the relevant government agencies before setting up their business. Others have argued that it is extremely important to dedicate some of your company's resources to marketing your products or services through a variety of channels. In addition, beginners were also advised to create a structured internal professional environment, to create networks and to be open to new or innovative ideas.

Other respondents pointed out that the lack of a corporate culture in terms of human capacity building and support for potential growth was a major challenge. As a result, new entrepreneurs need to develop the skills of their staff in order to remove the inefficiencies caused by a lack of technical and managerial skills, or to take advantage of local economies of scale in terms of energy, transport and security or raw materials.

Another recommendation from respondents was that youth SMEs should also strive to find and properly utilize information regarding local, regional and international pricing as well as about the regulatory environment in Rwanda and regionally in order to improve their business planning.

Chapter Summary

Most of the respondents 5.5% and 10.3% had challenges of credit access from financial institutions and the Business Development Fund (BDF) respectively. Access to entrepreneurial education by entrepreneurs before starting business was poor especially at Primary and Secondary school levels. 72% of youth entrepreneurs had no access to entrepreneurship education before starting business. A majority of youth (73.8%) had no access to Business Development services prior and after commencing business. Most youth 82.8% had serious problems with market access because they did not have market connections to market goods and services from their enterprises. A majority (57.9%) of respondents were in business due lack of employment and economic pressures.

IV. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

Introduction

This chapter presents a summary of findings, discussions, conclusions and recommendations based on the objectives of the study. Youth entrepreneurship has been identified as a major source of employment, given the high youth unemployment rate. The purpose of this study was to examine the effects of availability and accessibility of credit, access to entrepreneurship education and training, business development services, access market and market access and socio-economic factors influence the development of entrepreneurship among young people.

Based on the responses provided by the respondents, the researcher generated results that were used to draw conclusions and make recommendations. The main conclusions are based on the results of the data analysis in Chapter five, as shown in the summary table in (6.5).

Summary table

Objectives	Findings
1. To determine how credit availability and accessibility from various institutions influence the development of youth in Nyanza District.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Youth access of credit from Banks was 5.5% which is quite low due to high interest rates. ✓ Individual access of funds from BDF was 10.3% and quite low due to stringent requirement.
2. To examine how access to entrepreneurship education and training influence the development of entrepreneurship among the youth in Nyanza District.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Most youth (72.4%) had no access to entrepreneurship education prior to starting business ✓ Provision of entrepreneurship education at primary and secondary level was quite poor. ✓ Most respondents (35.9%) and (30.3%) suggested that entrepreneurship education starts mainly at the primary and secondary levels respectively.
3. To determine how access to Business development services influence the development of entrepreneurship among the youth in Nyanza District.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Most youth (73.8%) had no access to business support services prior and after starting business. ✓ Most preferred to have received these services prior to starting business.
4. To establish how access to markets influence the development of entrepreneurship among the youth in Nyanza District.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Most youth had problems accessing markets due to unfair tender allocation (42.8%) and stiff competition (31%). ✓ Majority of youth (82.8%) had no business connections to market their goods and services. ✓ Majority of respondents (85.5%) had no organization or institution helping them to market their products, while only 2.1% received help from marketing companies.
5. To examine the social, political and economic factors influencing the development of entrepreneurship among the youth in Nyanza District.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 58.6% of the youth revealed that the socio economic environment was not supportive. ✓ 71.7% of respondents had difficulty complying with government regulations and policies due to tougher taxation, licensing, patent/copyright laws as well as Competition regulations. ✓ Most youth (57.9) were in business due to lack of formal employment

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ In addition, the rate of entrepreneurship of among the youth increases with age.
6. Statistical analysis between Youth Entrepreneurship Development and its determinants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ It is observed that all variables have high positive correlation coefficients which were also statistically significant: Access to Business Development Services has the highest correlation coefficient of 0.993, followed by Access to Market (0.988), Access to credits (0.986), Socio-economic factors (0.985) and Access to Entrepreneurship Education and training (0.945). ✓ All Chi Square values were zero which is strongly significant on both the 1% and 5% levels ✓ R Square of 1 is extremely very good which means that 100% of our values fit the regression analysis model. ✓ The F value of zero was also Significant which indicates statistical reliability of the study results.

Table 6.1: Summary of findings

V. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section gives a detailed discussion of the findings from this study.

Credit availability and accessibility

Sustained entrepreneurship requires supportive and accessible financial institutions, such as commercial banks, development finance institutions, microfinance banks, credit bureaus, and money deposit banks (Omoruyi et al., 2017). However, Chigunta (2002) has argued that lack of access to finance is one of the main issues facing youth-run businesses around the world. This was confirmed by the findings of this study where most respondents had access to funding, but access to credit from banks and the Business Development Fund was problematic. Only 5.5% of young respondents had access to start-up capital from banks and 10.3% from the Business Development Fund. Those who could not obtain funding from the Business Development Fund on

an individual basis attributed it to the strict conditions imposed while others complained about the high interest rate and the lack of collaterals as the reason behind their inability to obtain credit from financial institution.

On the other hand, Financiers, nevertheless, claim that most youth ventures simply are not fundable or do not seem viable. This aligns with Essayed (2005) who found that formal financial institutions generally consider young people to be high-risk creditors and are reluctant to provide credit on favorable terms. Omoruyi et al. (2017) are very keen on the fact that financial institutions demand outrageous collaterals as a condition sine qua non for extending investment loans, which hinder aspiring youth entrepreneurs. While the Rwandan government claims to have put in place appropriate capital ventures (MINECOFIN, 2013), the business development fund (BDF) officials, on their side, cite in particular the lack of a good business plan, the quality and feasibility of the business idea, and the perceived commitment of the entrepreneur as the reason for the slow process (Donah & Marie Grace, 2019). This may be linked to a New Times Reporter's, Timothy (2014), finding that young people's access to financial services in the form of loans and grants has by far been a major challenge, largely because of their lack of experience in running businesses.

However, given the important role that youth entrepreneurs are expected to play in the national economic growth, it is still imperative for the government to strengthen policies that increase efforts to reduce the financing constraints of potential youth entrepreneurs. The question is how this long-standing problem would be better addressed in the national programs.

Entrepreneurship education and training

Entrepreneurship education and training is essential for the growth and development of youth entrepreneurship. School (2006) suggested that entrepreneurship education is essential to help

young people develop entrepreneurial attributes and behaviors that allow them to recognize entrepreneurship as a career option. According to the findings of the study, the supply of entrepreneurship training was still rather low, with only 27.6% having access to it before starting their own business. This may be attributable to the fact that entrepreneurship education is not offered at the primary level, whereas it is offered in secondary school as an optional subject and is more theoretical than practical.

The World Bank (2002) found that pedagogy of entrepreneurship education remained limited to traditional classroom teaching, even though the expected outcome is to teach students how to create and manage a business. This aligns with Omoruyi et al. (2017) who claim that the limited pool of skilled managerial talent is in most situation connected to the education system. According to them: “*Numerous African education systems centre on preparing the workforce for employment by more-established companies*”.

The Rwanda young entrepreneurs, on their side, recognize the importance of entrepreneurship education and training to permit them to succeed in opening or growing a business. Most respondents proposed for the provision of entrepreneurship education in Rwanda mainly at the primary level (35.9%) and 30.3 % at secondary school level. This denote that entrepreneurs need a skilled workforce to meet their business targets, by link the strategy of action in the minds of young people the conceptual knowledge and technical skills required in adulthood to constantly be in action, innovate and manage with the best guarantees of efficiency.

Business development services

The study found that only 26.2% of respondents had access to business development services before starting their own business. This may be due to the fact that few private sector actors are

involved in providing these services. According to the study findings, 73.1% of business development services provided to youth came from government. The commercial development services provided were in the form of management, ICT, marketing and accounting. According to School (2006), young people's access to business development services, such as mentoring, support networks, business clubs and incubators, increases the chances of sustaining their businesses beyond the star-up phase. However, young entrepreneurs often lack the support services needed to turn fragile start-up businesses into successful small and medium-sized enterprises. School (2006) also suggested that business incubators are a powerful tool to support the entrepreneurial process and increase the survival rate of innovative start-ups. Lack of business development services can have a significant impact.

Market availability and accessibility

According to this study, young people faced different types of problems when they marketed their goods and services with an unfair contracts/tender allocation, taking 48.2%, probably because of corruption and nepotism. The fierce competition was the second serious challenge with 31%.

Although the Rwandan government, according to the BDF status report (2015), is committed to supporting youth-led businesses with at least 10% of its procurement needs, this is still insufficient given the fierce competition in the market. With regard to market access assistance, the government's efforts in this regard are still lacking. According to the BDF status report (2015), the government has so far been able to help 1800 young people to market their products only at local trade fairs and 32 other young people exhibit their products at international trade fairs.

Social Economic Factors

Socio-economic factors can have different influences on the development of youth entrepreneurship. Based on the results of the study, it is clear that participation in entrepreneurship activities increases with age, with youngest entrepreneurs (47.6%) aged between 31 and 35 years old. Those aged between 18-21 year olds accounted for 6.8%, perhaps because most youth in this age group are likely to go to school or have not yet chosen their career path.

The results of this study revealed that 57.9% of young respondents were in business because of lack of formal jobs, while 10.3% were in business to supplement their income. This conclusion is consistent with that of the Chigunta (2001) survey in Zambia, which revealed that an overwhelming majority (92.3%) of respondents cited socio-economic issues as the main reason for creating the business, while nearly half (46.2%) of lack of employment, one-third (30.8%) the need to supplement household income; and 15.4% of poverty. Similarly, Charles and Charles (2018) point out that the Rwandan culture does not encourage entrepreneurial mind-set which is a firm's wealth and success creating factor that enables entrepreneurs to make optimal decisions in case of uncertainties. This explains why young people engage in business seeking economic survival in absence of formal employment. The fact that entrepreneurial activity increases with age can also be explained by the fact that at the age of majority, young people assume more and more responsibilities, hence engaging in small business as a coping mechanism.

Government Policies and Regulations

Unfavorable government policies and regulations can be a major obstacle to the development of youth entrepreneurship. In this study, 57.2% of the young respondents revealed that tax laws were a very serious barrier for youth-run businesses, while licensing regulations came in second with 48.3%. According to School (2006), unfavorable tax systems can lead to the collapse of start-

ups during their first years of existence. High tax rates reduce corporate profits, increasing the cost of doing business. A 2005 World Bank study confirms the findings of this study that tax regulations, licensing and associated costs are still heavy in most developing countries for youth-led enterprises.

However, Sabine (2014) who analysed Rwandan Policy documents, found that Policy initiatives are being initiated by different actors to help enterprises to overcome start up and scale up challenges. For the SMEs policy document, the Government created initiatives such as simplifying the fiscal and regulatory framework for SMEs growth, reduce taxes for enterprises and easy access of SMEs to financial services. According to her (Sabine), the Rwanda competition and consumer protection policy highlighted the need to further reduce barriers to entry into any sector of the economy or to any form of economic activity. The Industrial policy document emphasized the role of good governance and zero-tolerance to corruption to promote competition in the country.

According to Sabine (2014), government policies and regulations provides and influence an enabling environment for youth business startup and growth. After analyzing some policy documents, she (Sabine) found that Rwandan policy documents discuss on an enabling investment environment for enterprises to start up and scale up their businesses in all types of industries in general. In the SMEs policy document, for startup and growth, enterprises need to operate in a country as much attractive as possible to business investment and innovation. There is a need to create an enabling environment with skilled entrepreneurs, favorable regulatory framework, improved access to finance and targeted opportunities and incentives. Youth SMEs need also to be further supported to access financial services and to see the fiscal and regulatory framework alleviated. For a positive competition benefiting to producers and consumers, the Rwanda

Competition and Consumer Protection policy document is highlighting the need to develop clear policies and legislation to foster a competitive environment for business enterprises. Incentives have to be provided to producers within the country for improvement of production and internally expose Rwanda enterprises for a more global competition. To promote competition, the government has also to reduce barriers to entry into any sector of the economy or to any form of economic activity. The industrial policy emphasis on the need for manufacturing industries to access affordable raw materials and inputs and to see different industry projects being supported in order to promote the industrial sector.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

The finding of this research have confirmed that Rwandan young entrepreneurs face a variety of real barriers such as: Lack of awareness of potential for entrepreneurship among role models results in a lack of encouragement or even negative social attitudes; entrepreneurship Education and training programmes generally do not do enough to nurture entrepreneurial attitudes and skills; Lack of prior work and entrepreneurship experience is a major determinant to business startup and entrepreneurship performance; Fewer financial resources and difficulty obtaining external finance, including debt finance, hampers business start-up; Limited business networks and business-related social capital have consequences for business start-up and obtaining legitimacy; and finally Market barriers, including a bias in financial markets away from supporting youth-owned businesses and ‘discrimination’ in product markets.

The following conclusions were drawn from the findings of this study. To effectively promote the development of youth entrepreneurship, it is necessary to take into account the particular needs of young people when formulating government policies on economic activities, in order to take full advantage of the potential of SMEs as a factor contributing to employment in the economy.

Poor access to credit and unavailability may slow down the development of youth entrepreneurship if there are no favorable credit systems to promote youth entrepreneurship. State-sponsored youth credit schemes should be designed to overcome the many problems they face, such as corruption.

The provision of entrepreneurship education and training should also be improved at all levels of learning, especially at the primary and secondary levels, where it is lacking or insufficient. Another factor that needs to be strengthened to effectively develop youth entrepreneurship is the provision of business development services such as mentoring, business counseling and training. The development of youth entrepreneurship may be affected by the low accessibility of youth-led products to the market.

The existence of unfavorable government policies such as: Taxation, patent laws and licensing regulations also constitute a major obstacle to the development of youth entrepreneurship. These call for the establishment of favorable regulations and trade policies for youth-run enterprises, as well as to help them market their products.

Policy Implication and Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher made several recommendations to promote the development of youth entrepreneurship.

Improving Youth Availability and access to finance

The study indicated that the individual access of funds from BDF was also 10.3% and quite low due to stringent requirement. Recognizing that the promotion of youth entrepreneurship and self-employment requires increased access to credit by strengthening financial infrastructure, bank competition and non-bank financing (Samuel, 2012); it recommended that all Rwandan Government sponsored microcredit programs should be rethought to address weaknesses that hinder their effectiveness. Barriers for youth to access credit on an individual basis from financial institutions and programs should be addressed.

On the other hand, the overall youth access of credit from Banks and other financial institutions was 5.5% which is quite low due to high interest rates. In this regards, various institutional arrangements and incentive schemes can be used to widen access to credit. Thanking the case of Uganda, the Development Finance Company of Uganda Bank Limited's (DFCU) credit facility is largely provided under a leasing arrangement. Evidence shows that having credit and financial services that are accessible to women is crucial for increasing their ability to save and start a business (Dupas and Robinson 2013). Similarly, in Kenya and Uganda, M-Pesa and Mobile Money respectively have been central to providing financial access to a wide section of the unbanked population. This call for Rwanda to uphold the best practices when addressing the issue of youth entrepreneurship.

Furthermore, it should be recognized that young people do not necessarily start small or marginal economic activities (Dr. Jonathan & David,2014). The activity they can put in place depends on their talents, resources, entrepreneurial abilities and aspirations. This can range from

livelihood activities generating additional income to self-employment, microenterprises and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Therefore, not all financial services are adequate for each of these types. In this regard, there should be a clear distinction between various economic activities to make effective use of financial services.

Figure 8.4: Various youth economic activities

Source: Dr. Jonathan Potter and David Halabisky (2014)

This classification should be considered a continuum because there is always overlap between categories. However, evidence suggests that there are virtually no independent graduates, but also small or medium-sized enterprises. People do not necessarily spend all their time on one activity for the rest of their lives. They can operate as a small entrepreneur for several years, then choose to work officially or even combine self-employment with other formal work. Such hybrid and mixed forms are used more and more frequently. For young people, these hybrids and mixed forms can offer new opportunities, therefore, support programs should be adapted to them and policies should allow it.

Financial support

- Financial support should be adaptive to the context (person etc);
- Financial support should be linked with mentoring, though this should be adapted to specific circumstances;
- The system should be sufficiently flexible to give diversified financial support linked to the specific needs of the company: e.g. start-up seed capital, loans for companies for growth etc, subsidies for technological development;
- Finance should not be a substitute for having both a good idea and a good person running it;
- Both clients and suppliers need to understand financing and financial management.

Promoting Youth Access to entrepreneurship education and training

Most of the survey youth entrepreneurs (72.4%) had no access to entrepreneurship education prior and after starting business. To these end majority of them suggested the provision of entrepreneurship education at primary and secondary level was quite poor. Therefore, Entrepreneurship education and training programs should be introduced at primary and secondary school levels, where they are non-existent or inadequate. These programs should be adapted to give young people the skills they need to start their own business and not just write exams. The most effective entrepreneurship training should combine 'core' business administration skills, such as accounting, with 'softer' entrepreneurial skills, such as problem solving. It is important to systematically screen youth for latent or active entrepreneurial characteristics, such as innovative thinking, leadership attributes, passion and results orientation. Programmes should clearly separate

training and financing functions by forming partnerships with financial institutions to provide and manage credit for youth (MIF 2012). To improve entrepreneurs' ability to benefit from trade liberalization and foreign investment, they also need skills for developing their networks and linking with higher levels of the value chain.

Training centers

In the context of Rwanda where the Business Development Fund (BDF) provides small scale Business development services and micro-loans, Entrepreneurship Centers can be suggested at least in each district. The center should partner with financial institutions over the provision of credits to young people completing a wide range of trainings, who lack access to business capital but have convincing business proposals. A District entrepreneurship center should be a youth-run social enterprise serving as guarantee to its own member, which reduces the insolvency risk for the financial institution. Given that the district entrepreneurship center provides continuous business development services to its youth members, the collaborating financial institution will hope for a reduced risk of business failure and increased chance of loan repayment.

Furthermore, the programme should find innovative ways to lessen the financial burden imposed on individual youth by being active members of the programme. This can be done through intensification of fund raising strategies. One of the strategies to increase fundraising is to seek corporate sponsorship to host fundraising dinners, galas, concerts, sports events, raffle tickets and more.

Training centers and schools' partnerships

The Rwandan education system has been associated with the uncompetitive performance of young graduates in the labor market. The weakness of entrepreneurship training for youth

entrepreneurs is mainly based on different aspects, such as the difficulties linking the subjects taught to the context (regional, national); Lack of inter-institutional and inter-university coordination, Lack of appropriate tools and pedagogical resources, Unsuitable pedagogy; Lack of specialized trainers / instructors; Very heterogeneous and often inappropriate contents; Confusion related to module titles; etc. Additionally, a recent OECD (2012) report pointed out that university education is much more limited to inexperience of the faculty members/teachers who try their best but who are not familiar with the problems, the literature and sometimes even lack the basic pedagogical tools (if they come from outside of the university); Little or no impact on the students, which sometimes reflects a lack of interest for the subject and the phenomenon and / or the overly academic contents, which do not include enough professional input (knowledge and know-how).

This partnership is one of the most essential strategies to help education providers and employers work together to address all of these challenges. The partnership will also help universities to create internships and secure apprenticeships for their students to support students' learning to prepare them for the workplace and to support the application of classroom learning on the job. By partnering with entrepreneurship centers the universities ensure that students get started on a long term entrepreneurship career path while they are still in college rather than wait for them to venture into business post-graduation, and serve as an incubation service for the businesses that the students want to start. This strategy will help to ensure that the mentorship programme starts while the students are still in college.

On the other hand, this programme should ensure that enough time is allocated for activities. One strategy is to partner with tertiary institutions and offer a joint programme wherein students received certificates which are officially recognized by relevant bodies such as Ministry of

Education and workforce Development Authority (WDA). This will also dispel the feelings by participating youth that the programme affects their core study.

Through entrepreneurship center universities and education providers would be helped to develop and strengthen the structures and protocol for internship and job placement, modifying and implementing a revised internship and career coaching model that increases various stakeholder engagement. Education providers are expected not only to benefit from apprenticeship opportunities but also work with entrepreneurship centers to create or access careers-based courses.

Instilling entrepreneurship mind-set

The fact that most youth respondents (57.9) were in business due to lack of formal employment, this data suggests lack of entrepreneurial mind-set. Therefore, entrepreneurship curriculums should focus on developing entrepreneurial mind-sets. Training should encourage attitudinal changes. Training approaches should include learning by doing, experimentation and being prepared to accept failure and learn from it.

The practice of effective small business ownership and entrepreneurship includes a variety of different qualities. These include:

- Possessing the knowledge and professional practice to run a business: (e.g. competency development finance). The literature suggests that students for example need to possess different ‘resource logics’ of other entrepreneurs (Politis et al., 2013).

- Skills and attitudes: behavioral (e.g. leadership technical). Younger people may have the determination and enthusiasm to run a business but do they have the appropriate skills-set and leadership qualities? Hence programmes should take this into consideration.
- Meta-qualities: (e.g. ability to reflect on self-knowledge, collect new knowledge). How do younger people differ from other groups of the population? When seeking to enhance skills and competencies, particular attention should be given to
- Enhancing the means to practice entrepreneurship (raising the ability to mobilize resources) and filling gaps in social and financial capital. These are particular issues for younger people, given their shorter periods of time in work.
- Identification of wider cultural and social networks. Socio-economic-cultural contexts are important, e.g. Females, minority groups, low-income, high income localities. These will add further complexity to the development of training and mentoring programmes for younger people.

Methods of training and mentoring

Training and mentoring programs should be delivered in different ways. These can range from traditional means of information transfer (classroom, distance learning, independent study) to interactions with peers and key agents of the business support network. These actual delivery methods should be associated with different types of learning. For example:

- The development of behavioral and human capital can be enhanced by role plays and problem-solving exercises.

- Meta-qualities such as confidence and leadership can be developed through action learning sets; develop the ability of learning to learn; and identify the weaknesses of oneself for subsequent development

Formal approaches need also to be complemented by tacit learning with peers and networks.

These may involve, for example:

- Partnership involvement: meetings with financiers, banks, landlords, incubators, trade and professional organizations
- Mentoring with peers – young people who have actually started and run a business
- Face-to-face interaction effective
- Connecting youth with knowledge networks

Although there are many learning theories, they should be interpreted with caution for specific situations and population groups. For the youngest, because the knowledge base is not perfect and is constantly evolving with the latest ideas and modes of delivery (e.g. Royal Society of Arts 2013, Valero et al., 2014), there should be documentation of their training gaps, how their entrepreneurial potential can be measured, the content of the program and how this should be best delivered.

Promoting Youth Access to Business development services

Most of the surveyed youth (73.8%) had no access to business support services prior and after starting business and Most preferred to have received these services prior to starting business. In this regards, the Business development services provided by the government should be spread across all regions of the country, even to the level of sector and cells. The private sector should

also complement government efforts in providing business development services. However, most importantly, there should be a coordination mechanism to coordinate these efforts to avoid duplications and ensure effectiveness. In addition, the range of business development services should be expanded to include incubation and business counseling.

Furthermore, it is also recommended that all youth entrepreneurship centers collaborate with youth empowerment institutions to coordinate and maximize their efforts. By linking with other training providers, youth empowerment and business organizations such as the Private sector federation (PSF), Youth Empowerment for Global Opportunities (YEGO Centers), Business Development Fund (BDF), NGOs, etc., will further boost confidence and inspire young people to venture into business as such meetings or interactions allow students to experience first-hand the challenges faced by successful entrepreneurs. As a strategy, empowerment programmes should arrange participation of teams on forums like International Trade Fair, Entrepreneurship Expo so as to give aspiring youth entrepreneurs a real life exposure.

Promoting Youth Access to Market

The study revealed that most youth had problems accessing markets due to unfair tender allocation (42.8%) and stiff competition (31%). This calls the government to improve its tendering system by making it easier for start-ups to win bids. To do so, the government is strongly encouraged to adopt an e-procurement system that automates the public procurement process and enable the interactions of Government to Business entities. All government institutions should publish tenders and invite bidders to submit their proposals via this system. This system should be able to ensure that evaluation of bids, contracts management and payments are done electronically. The system is expected to reduce the probability of loopholes and fraud in the procurement process.

This is partly because all transactions are done online and human contact is eliminated entirely in the process, hence enhancement of transparency and standardization of electronic documents, supplier registration and authentication, goods and services information and streamlines all elements of public procurement transactions. It should, in addition, increase its consumption of youth-led enterprise products to at least up to 50% in all of its ministries and semi-public agencies.

On the other hand, majority of youth (82.8%) had no business connections to market their goods and services. In this regard, it's strongly recommended that young people be facilitated to access market information, including market survey and analysis reports as well as labor market information. When market opportunities exist, youth can be helped by providing information and employment exchange services through educational institutions, or by offering these in youth entrepreneurship centers. Better access to information further requires the availability of transportation. For poorer youth and those living further from urban centres, offering transport subsidies may be necessary to allow them to benefit from employment exchange services and access information on entrepreneurship opportunities. In predominantly informal labour markets, however, formal information channels may be of little relevance. We know little about the functioning of informal labour markets, but it is clear that informal networks are key in the job searching process. The use of new technologies, particularly mobile phone-based, could help in expanding job search networks for youth, linking formal and informal networks, and increasing the effectiveness of these networks. Where growth is weak and there is a lack of productive jobs, overseas employment programmes may be part of a solution.

Networking

Networking opportunities should be created and networks should have inspirational members/mentors to motivate youth. Network should also combine people with different skills sets/profiles (though similar interests). There should be a link with professional support. In addition, the network should have clear aims and connection with other structures as well as a vision for the future (after the project/programme).

Improving Socio-economic environment

During the study youth revealed that their social environment wasn't encouraging at all where 58.6% of the youth revealed that the socio economic environment was not supportive and most youth respondent (57.9) were in business due to lack of formal employment. This suggests that engendering entrepreneurship should start with a mindset change towards a culture which rewards competition and innovation. This entails addressing the beliefs, values and attitudes underlying behaviour and choices. Effective mindset change begins with identifying prevailing mindsets. As such, honest discussions can provide hypotheses to be tested through surveys. While most economic development efforts shy away from explicitly addressing mindset change, this is an issue that some suggest is key to any real progress (The Brenthurst Foundation 2011).

Government Policy and regulations

As the study revealed that majority (71.7%) of young entrepreneurs find it difficult to comply with government policies and regulations, it is recommended that youth micro-entrepreneurship also requires reform and more consistent enforcement of business regulation, in order to reduce red tape and increase transparency (ILO 2012b). Government policies and regulations relating to commercial activities should be made more favorable to youth-run businesses through tax holidays for new businesses, as well as a relaxation of licensing regulations, especially at the level of

Rwanda Standard Board (RBS). The government should also allow business leaders to participate in the policy process so that they can contribute and learn about the interventions designed to help them.

Policy design and delivery by government and other providers

- There should be dialogue with target group and stakeholders;
- Clear objectives/outcomes/results/indicators are essential – and this should include mind-set change even if it cannot be measured during the project;
- Stakeholders should have clearly defined roles to avoid duplication and disputes;
- Invest in ongoing monitoring and evaluation to allow for fine tuning;
- There should be continuous focus on lessons learned to give feedback for future development e.g. limitations, resources, timelines;
- Active learning from pilot projects should run in different locations.

Suggestions for Future Research

This study proposes the following areas for further study;

- a) The impact of Business Development Fund on the growth of youth entrepreneurship in Rwanda.
- b) An assessment of the effectiveness of state sponsored credit programmes for youth run enterprises towards promotion of youth entrepreneurship in other parts of the country.

- c) An investigation into the effect of entrepreneurship education on the development of youth entrepreneurship in other parts of the country.
- d) To analyze the impact of existing entrepreneurship policies to increase investments in the country.
- e) Analysis of youth-led business performance with regard to the culture and entrepreneurial experience.

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